

Bronchoaspiration During Endoscopy Under Sedation in a Patient with a History of Gastrectomy and Prolonged Fasting: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Bronchoaspiration is defined as the inhalation of oropharyngeal or gastric contents into the lower respiratory tract, which may lead to different pulmonary syndromes. Although aspiration risk assessment is commonly based on fasting times, current clinical guidelines were developed for healthy patients undergoing elective surgery and are not reliable in patients with comorbidities that alter gastric kinetics. Non-operating room anesthesia (NORA) procedures further increase this risk due to the logistical challenges inherent to the environment.

Case presentation: A 63-year-old woman with a history of gastric adenocarcinoma treated with subtotal gastrectomy and Roux-en-Y reconstruction, chemotherapy, and radiotherapy subsequently developed post-radiation gastric stenosis, intestinal hypomotility, and delayed gastric emptying. Computed tomography revealed a markedly dilated stomach with persistent abundant food content, and diagnostic upper gastrointestinal endoscopy was indicated. During upper gastrointestinal endoscopy performed under sedation, abundant semisolid gastric contents were documented despite a reported fasting period of more than 36 hours. The patient developed regurgitation with bronchoaspiration and severe hypoxemia, requiring immediate advanced airway management. Chemical pneumonitis secondary to massive aspiration was diagnosed. The patient showed favorable clinical evolution without respiratory sequelae.

Conclusion: Preoperative fasting, even when prolonged, does not eliminate the risk of bronchoaspiration in patients with prior gastric surgery, oncologic disease, or impaired gastric emptying. The occurrence of a severe bronchoaspiration event in a NORA setting despite strict adherence to fasting protocols highlights the importance of individualized anesthetic assessment, consideration of additional airway protection strategies, and the potential use of gastric ultrasound for more accurate risk stratification.

KEYWORDS: Bronchoaspiration; Aspiration pneumonitis; Non-operating room anesthesia; Delayed gastric emptying; Prolonged fasting.

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INTRODUCTION

Bronchoaspiration is defined as the inhalation of oropharyngeal or gastric contents, either liquid or solid, into the larynx and the lower respiratory tract. Following aspiration, several pulmonary syndromes may occur depending on the quantity and nature of the aspirated material, the frequency of aspiration, and the host response to the aspirated material. Aspiration pneumonitis (Mendelson's syndrome) is a chemical injury caused by the inhalation of

sterile gastric contents, whereas aspiration pneumonia is an infectious process caused by the inhalation of oropharyngeal secretions colonized by pathogenic bacteria. Although some overlap exists between these syndromes, they represent distinct clinical entities.^{1,3}

Non-operating room anesthesia (NORA) refers to the administration of sedation or anesthesia outside the traditional operating room for patients undergoing painful or diagnostic procedures. These procedures are increasing due

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to technological advances in medical equipment, improved procedural expertise, and the growing number of medically complex patients. Major challenges unique to NORA include those related to the patient, the procedure, and the environment. Physicians unfamiliar with NORA often underestimate the fact that patients undergoing procedures involving new and advanced technological equipment may present increased risk. These patients include pediatric and geriatric populations as well as medically complex patients who may be too fragile for surgical management but may benefit from a procedural intervention. The anesthesiologist must understand the nature of the procedure, including patient positioning, the expected degree of pain, and its duration. In addition, prior discussion with the procedural physician should include contingency plans for emergencies and adverse outcomes.^{2,4}

Aspiration risk assessment is commonly based on fasting times; however, fasting guidelines do not apply to urgent or emergent situations or to patients with certain comorbidities. One of the main risk factors for aspiration is the presence of residual gastric contents. The critical threshold of gastric fluid volume that alone increases aspiration risk remains controversial, but healthy fasting patients frequently present residual gastric volumes up to 1.5 ml/kg without a significant increase in aspiration risk. These guidelines apply only to healthy patients undergoing elective surgery and are not reliable in patients with coexisting diseases that affect gastric emptying or gastric volume.⁵

In patients with anatomical or functional alterations of the gastrointestinal tract, such as previous gastric surgery, radiotherapy, or motility disorders, gastric emptying may be significantly impaired, favoring retention of gastric contents even after prolonged fasting periods, thereby increasing the risk of bronchoaspiration during procedures performed under sedation.^{5,6} In this context, we present the case of an oncologic patient with a history of partial gastrectomy who developed severe bronchoaspiration during upper gastrointestinal endoscopy under non-operating room anesthesia despite prolonged fasting of more than 36 hours. This case highlights the limitations of traditional fasting criteria and the need for individualized anesthetic assessment in high-risk patients through objective diagnostic tools for the detection of a full stomach, such as gastric ultrasound, as well as adequately trained personnel in its use.

CASE REPORT

A 63-year-old female patient of mestizo ethnicity, born and residing in Mérida, Yucatán, Mexico, a lawyer by profession with university education and single marital status, was evaluated. Her relevant medical history included a diagnosis in 2017 of poorly differentiated intestinal-type gastric adenocarcinoma treated with subtotal gastrectomy with Roux-en-Y reconstruction, followed by chemotherapy (18 cycles, regimen unspecified) and radiotherapy (28 sessions).

Since then, she developed chronic digestive complications including post-radiation gastric stenosis, intestinal hypomotility, and delayed gastric emptying, which required multiple prior endoscopic dilation procedures. She had no chronic degenerative diseases, denied tobacco, alcohol, or illicit drug use, and had no family history of gastrointestinal malignancies.

From a psychosocial perspective, the patient remained functional and independent, although her diet was limited due to food intolerance related to her gastrointestinal condition. She reported regular consumption of herbal infusions (chamomile and rosemary). She was in a state of malnutrition, with a body mass index of 17 kg/m² and progressive, unquantified weight loss.

As part of the diagnostic workup for suspected tumor recurrence, contrast-enhanced computed tomography of the chest and abdomen was performed. The study revealed a markedly dilated stomach with abundant food content and an air–fluid level, thickening of the pyloric antrum suggestive of tumor infiltration, dilated jejunal loops, and postsurgical changes consistent with partial gastrectomy with gastrojejunostomy, without evidence of metastatic disease or acute pulmonary findings. Based on these findings, diagnostic upper gastrointestinal endoscopy was indicated.

The patient initially attended the procedure with a 12-hour fasting period; however, it was postponed after abundant semisolid gastric contents were identified during endoscopy. The procedure was subsequently rescheduled. In the days preceding the second appointment, the patient reported nonspecific symptoms including early satiety, postprandial fullness, and intermittent episodes of mild vomiting. She returned one week later. On this second occasion, the preoperative fasting period was 36 hours by the patient's own decision due to fear of another postponement. This fasting period was verified through medical documentation and confirmation by a family member. No gastric content aspiration or gastric ultrasound assessment was performed prior to the procedure.

During the pre-anesthetic evaluation, the patient was conscious, oriented, and cooperative. Airway evaluation revealed no predictors of difficult airway. The anesthetic plan, benefits, risks, and potential complications were explained, and informed consent was obtained.

The patient was transferred to the endoscopy suite and initially positioned in the right lateral decubitus position. Continuous noninvasive monitoring was initiated, and supplemental oxygen was administered via nasal cannula at 3 L/min. Initial vital signs were: blood pressure 106/70 mmHg, heart rate 61 bpm, respiratory rate 16 breaths/min, and oxygen saturation 98%. Topical airway anesthesia was performed with lidocaine spray, and intravenous sedation was initiated with fentanyl 50 µg, propofol 40 mg, and lidocaine 30 mg.

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An Olympus EVIS Exera GIF-HQ190 video gastroscope was introduced orally. Endoscopic examination revealed an esophagus with preserved shape, volume, and distensibility, and intact mucosa throughout its length. The squamocolumnar junction was identified at 38 cm from the upper dental arch, coinciding with the diaphragmatic pinch, with no evidence of hiatal hernia or esophagitis. The stomach showed altered anatomy due to prior surgery, with abundant semisolid food residues preventing complete mucosal examination. The gastrojejunostomy was identified and found to be patent, with a jejunal loop showing a linear ulcer covered with fibrin.

During gastric exploration, the patient suddenly developed regurgitation with evident bronchoaspiration, leading to immediate termination of the procedure.

The event was accompanied by severe hypoxemia, with oxygen saturation dropping to 37%. Immediate advanced airway management was initiated. Rapid sequence induction was performed with fentanyl 200 µg, propofol 100 mg, and rocuronium 50 mg. Videolaryngoscopy revealed abundant solid and liquid gastric contents in the airway, which were rigorously suctioned before successful orotracheal intubation with a 7.0 mm internal diameter endotracheal tube.

Invasive mechanical ventilation was initiated using lung-protective strategies with tidal volumes of 6 ml/kg predicted body weight, plateau pressure below 30 cm H₂O, and PEEP of 5 cm H₂O. Inhalational anesthesia with sevoflurane was started, leading to progressive recovery of oxygen saturation; however, an FiO₂ of 100% was required to maintain oxygen saturation above 92%. Therapeutic bronchial lavage was

performed until clear aspirate was obtained. Alveolar recruitment maneuvers were avoided due to the risk of worsening lung injury.

The patient was subsequently transferred to the intensive care unit for monitoring. On admission, she was hemodynamically stable without vasopressor requirement, on controlled mechanical ventilation with adequate oxygenation. Physical examination revealed isolated wheezing on pulmonary auscultation without crackles. Subsequent arterial blood gas analyses were normal, and the patient remained afebrile. Post-event chest radiography showed no evidence of pneumonic consolidation or pleural effusion.

Management included temporary ventilatory support, systemic corticosteroids, and nebulized therapy. Empirical antibiotic therapy was initiated early but discontinued once respiratory infection was ruled out. The patient showed favorable clinical evolution and was successfully extubated without complications after 72 hours. She was later transferred to the hospital ward, where she remained under observation for one week without respiratory deterioration.

The final diagnosis was bronchoaspiration syndrome (chemical pneumonitis) secondary to massive gastric content aspiration during sedation in a non-operating room procedure, precipitated by anatomical and functional alterations of the gastrointestinal tract despite prolonged fasting. Short-term respiratory prognosis was favorable; however, the overall prognosis was considered guarded in the medium term due to suspected tumor recurrence, malnutrition, and the high risk of future aspiration events during subsequent procedures.

Figure 1. Upper gastrointestinal endoscopy showing abundant retained semisolid gastric contents despite prolonged fasting in a patient with a history of partial gastrectomy and impaired gastric emptying. The procedure was discontinued due to regurgitation and high risk of bronchoaspiration.

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DISCUSSION

The American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) guidelines for preoperative fasting establish minimum fasting times and recommend a comprehensive clinical assessment to reduce the risk of pulmonary aspiration. However, these guidelines were designed for healthy patients undergoing elective procedures. The guidelines themselves acknowledge that they may not be applicable in patients with conditions that alter gastric emptying or gastric volume. In this context, patients with previous gastric surgery, gastrointestinal motility disorders, or oncologic disease cannot be reliably stratified using traditional fasting criteria, as illustrated in the present case.⁴

Van de Putte et al. reported that pulmonary aspiration of gastric contents remains one of the leading causes of mortality related to airway management, and that a significant proportion of these events occurs due to failure to recognize the actual risk of aspiration and to establish an appropriate airway protection strategy. The authors emphasize that the presence of gastric contents at the time of anesthetic induction is one of the main risk factors for aspiration, and that verification of fasting based solely on clinical history may be insufficient, even in the immediate preoperative period.⁵ In this context, gastric ultrasound has emerged as a bedside assessment tool that allows more accurate aspiration risk stratification and may significantly modify anesthetic management. This is particularly relevant in patients at high risk for gastric retention, such as those with previous gastric surgery, oncologic disease, or impaired gastric emptying, as in our case. However, it should also be noted that in our patient the history of gastrectomy may have limited the quantitative ultrasonographic assessment of gastric contents, although qualitative assessment would likely still have been feasible. Further studies are therefore required to clarify the usefulness of this tool in this subgroup of patients.

Jun D. Parker reported a case of pulmonary aspiration occurring during procedural sedation for diagnostic colonoscopy, triggered by a change in patient positioning. The case described a 72-year-old woman undergoing elective colonoscopy under propofol sedation who expelled a large amount of non-particulate gastric contents through the oropharynx when repositioned from the left lateral decubitus position to the supine position, accompanied by immediate oxygen desaturation below 90%. Unlike the traditional management of aspiration under general anesthesia, the event was successfully treated without endotracheal intubation.⁷ This report highlights that gastrointestinal endoscopy under procedural sedation represents a high-risk scenario for bronchoaspiration, particularly during positional changes, and that aspiration occurring in this context may require therapeutic considerations different from those under general anesthesia, findings consistent with those observed in our case.

Khan et al. conducted a scoping review of adverse events and near-miss events in non-operating room anesthesia (NORA), identifying wide variability in the reported incidence of complications associated with procedures performed in this environment, with rates ranging from 0.01% to 38.6%. The authors noted that this variability partly reflects heterogeneity in event definitions and the lack of high-quality prospective studies. They also highlighted that near-miss events occur more frequently than reported, suggesting that the real risk associated with NORA may be underestimated.⁸ These findings underscore the need for research specifically focused on safety in anesthesia outside the operating room, particularly in high-risk and rapidly expanding scenarios such as gastrointestinal endoscopy. They also support the notion that serious complications such as bronchoaspiration, as observed in the present case, may be underreported. This further emphasizes the importance of implementing hospital-specific protocols aimed at early recognition, treatment, and prevention of such events, as well as ensuring adequate training of personnel working in high-risk NORA settings.

Green et al. conducted the first comprehensive systematic review of pulmonary aspiration during procedural sedation, identifying 35 articles describing aspiration events in patients of all ages. Among the 292 episodes that occurred during gastrointestinal endoscopic procedures, eight deaths were reported. In contrast, aspiration during non-endoscopic procedures was infrequent and generally associated with complete recovery. The authors highlighted that although aspiration during procedural sedation is generally uncommon, gastrointestinal endoscopy accounts for the majority of reported events and the most severe outcomes, suggesting that this type of procedure represents a particularly high-risk scenario.⁹ Our case occurred during a gastrointestinal endoscopy similar to those reported in this review, the setting in which most aspiration events and the most severe outcomes occur. The presence of oncologic disease and delayed gastric emptying likely increased the risk of aspiration despite prolonged fasting.

Among the strengths of the management in this case was the prompt recognition of bronchoaspiration during a procedure performed in a non-operating room anesthesia environment, as well as the immediate initiation of respiratory support measures and airway protection, which helped limit the progression of pulmonary injury. In addition, proper documentation of the event and its subsequent analysis provide valuable information for identifying risk factors in complex patients. However, this case also presents important limitations, including the absence of an objective tool for gastric content assessment such as gastric ultrasound. Furthermore, the lack of continuous capnography monitoring represents a limitation inherent to the non-operating room anesthesia setting. Another limitation was the exclusive reliance on fasting time as a safety criterion, which may have

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underestimated the true risk of aspiration in a patient outside the target population for international fasting guidelines. Therefore, an important area of improvement in settings where NORA is performed is the availability of ultrasound equipment for gastric assessment, as well as properly trained personnel capable of performing and interpreting the examination.

Preoperative fasting, even when prolonged, is not a reliable predictor of an empty stomach in patients with prior gastric surgery, gastrointestinal motility disorders, or oncologic disease. Despite fasting for more than 36 hours, significant gastric retention was documented, highlighting the discrepancy between fasting-based recommendations and the actual pathophysiology of this patient. Furthermore, this case emphasizes that gastrointestinal endoscopy performed under sedation in a NORA setting represents a high-risk scenario for bronchoaspiration and that anesthetic evaluation must extend beyond traditional fasting criteria. Finally, it underscores the need to consider additional strategies for prevention and airway protection in high-risk patients. The availability of trained personnel and ultrasound equipment for gastric evaluation should be considered essential requirements for the safe practice of anesthesia outside the operating room, thereby reducing risks and complications associated with conditions that impair gastric emptying.

The patient reported understanding the complication that occurred during the procedure and stated that she felt well cared for by the medical team and was very grateful despite the complications encountered.

CONCLUSION

This case demonstrates that preoperative fasting, even when prolonged, does not eliminate the risk of bronchoaspiration in patients with prior gastric surgery, oncologic disease, or delayed gastric emptying undergoing endoscopy under sedation in a non-operating room anesthesia setting. In these scenarios, anesthetic evaluation must extend beyond traditional fasting criteria and should include individualized risk stratification through the use of gastric ultrasound, as well as additional preventive strategies and appropriate airway protection measures in order to reduce severe respiratory complications.

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Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Ethical Considerations: The patient's family member was informed at all times about the diagnosis, the interventions performed, and the potential risks. Written informed consent was obtained for the surgical and anesthetic procedures as well as for the publication of this case report, in accordance

with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and the institutional regulations of the hospital.

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